

SURGICAL OUTCOME OF PHACOEMULSIFICATION IN FOLDABLE VERSUS NON- FOLDABLE INTRAOCULAR LENS IN CATARACT PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background: Among the various modern cataract surgery techniques, phacoemulsification with foldable intraocular lens (IOL) implantation is most commonly performed. Foldable IOLs, owing to their smaller incisions potentially reduce Surgically induced astigmatism (SIA). Conversely, non-foldable IOLs might offer advantages such as affordability, particularly benefiting economically challenged individuals. **Aim:** To compare the visual outcomes and SIA after phacoemulsification with foldable versus non foldable IOL. **Method:** In a prospective, comparative, randomized clinical trial of phacoemulsification cataract surgery, 58 patients received hydrophilic foldable IOL through 2.8mm clear corneal incision and 58 patients received non foldable Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA) IOL through 6mm sclerocorneal tunnel. Preoperative and postoperative visual acuity at day 1, 1 month, and 3 month and SIA at 1 month, and 3 month follow up visits were analysed. **Results:** The post-operative UCVA at day 1 was 6/18 or better in 69.2% in group A and 76.0% in group B ($p = 0.294$). Post-operative BCVA at 4 weeks was 6/6-6/9 in 73.1% patients in group A and 84.0% patients in group B. The mean SIA at week 4 in group A was 1.10D (0.51SD) and 0.71D (0.32SD) in group B ($p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** Phacoemulsification with the implantation of a foldable IOL through a 2.8mm clear corneal incision results in less post-operative astigmatism compared to phacoemulsification with the implantation of a non-foldable IOL through a 6mm sclerocorneal tunnel. Thus phacoemulsification, whether paired with a foldable or rigid PMMA IOL, delivers excellent results when performed by experienced cataract surgeons.

Keywords: Phacoemulsification; Intraocular lenses; Visual Acuity; Surgically Induced Astigmatism.

INTRODUCTION

Senile cataract is the most prevalent form of visually significant cataract worldwide. ^(1,2) Any cataract surgery method's visual result can be evaluated in terms of the residual refractive error, which consists of both an astigmatic and spherical component. The spherical component can be predecided prior to surgery and is dependent on the desired lens power after surgery. Surgically induced astigmatism (SIA) is a significant barrier to obtaining good unassisted visual acuity. ^(3,4)

In the context of cataract surgery, Sheoran et al. defined SIA as the flattening effect along the axis caused by a corneal incision, which influences the refractive outcomes of the surgery. ⁽⁶⁾ This specific definition pertains solely to the impact of corneal incisions on astigmatism results. SIA requires patients to wear glasses after surgery for proper visual recovery, which is often undesirable due to the associated costs and inconvenience, leading to dissatisfaction among many patients. ^(5,6)

Foldable IOLs, owing to their smaller incisions and easier insertion, are anticipated to potentially reduce SIA. Conversely, non-foldable IOLs might offer advantages such as affordability, particularly benefiting economically challenged individuals who may not afford the costlier foldable IOLs. This study originated from the clinical observation that implanting an inexpensive rigid IOL after phacoemulsification seemed to produce visual outcomes comparable to those of more expensive foldable IOLs. This study aims to compare the visual outcomes and SIA after phacoemulsification using a 2.8 mm clear corneal incision with a foldable IOL versus a 6mm sclerocorneal tunnel with a rigid Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA) IOL.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Design and setting

This was a cross-sectional hospital based clinical study of 116 cataract patients to study astigmatism before and after phacoemulsification surgery in patients who presented to the department of Ophthalmology, Sharda hospital, Greater Noida between August 2022 to March 2024.

Inclusion criteria: Patients between 40-70 years of age, Cataract up to grade 3 according to Modified Lens Opacities Classification System

Exclusion criteria: Pre-existing corneal astigmatism (1 D and above), previous ocular surgeries such as corneal, pterygium or refractive surgeries or any other intraocular surgeries., amblyopic patients, history of ocular trauma, patients with associated glaucoma, optic atrophy, corneal opacity, macular pathologies.

Study tool

Written consent was taken from each patient. Detailed history including ocular history, general history, and family history was recorded for all patients. Comprehensive eye examination including Snellen's and logMAR visual acuity, Refraction, NCT, refraction, slit lamp examination, keratometry, biometry, and fundus examination was performed.

Huvitz HRK-1 Auto Refkeratometer was used for the purpose of keratometry and an A-Scan ultrasound for the purpose of axial length measurement. The power of the intra-ocular lens was calculated with the modified SRK/T formula. A total of 116 patients were included in the present study by simple Randomization.

Patients were divided equally into two groups on random basis:

- o Group A: Patients undergoing phacoemulsification with foldable IOL.
- o Group B: Patients undergoing phacoemulsification with PMMA IOL.

Surgical Technique: After pupil dilatation with tropicamide and phenylephrine eye drops, a peribulbar injection was given. Preoperative povidone iodine 5% solution was used for disinfection of the periocular skin area. All patients were operated by the same surgeon to avoid inter surgeon variation.

Phacoemulsification was done with Zeiss phaco visalis 500 machine with 2.8mm port. The size of main (superior clear corneal) incision was 2.8mm in group A patients with foldable IOL and (sclero-corneal tunnel) 6mm with non-foldable IOL in group B patients. The size of IOL optics was 6mm in both groups. Patients were evaluated on Post operative day 1, 1 month and 3 months. Continuous variables were expressed as mean and standard deviations (SD). Categorical variables were expressed as number and percentages. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered to indicate statistical significance. Post-hoc data analysis was performed using paired t-tests and Chi-square to compare quantitative variables.

Statistical software: The Statistical software namely SPSS 22.0 was used for the analysis of the data and Microsoft word and Excel have been used to generate graphs, tables etc.

RESULTS

A total of 116 patients were included in this study which were divided into two groups: Group A (Foldable IOL) and Group B (Non -foldable IOL).

Table 1: Clinical and socio-demographic parameters.

Variables	Group A Mean(SD) or N%	Group B Mean(SD) or N%	p value
Age (Years)	60.2±7.9	57.4±8.8	0.21
Male	29 (50.0%)	30 (51.7%)	0.92
Female	29 (50.0%)	28 (48.3%)	
Pre op BCVA			0.06
6/12	11(18.9%)	0(0.0%)	
6.18	10(17.2%)	25(43.1%)	
6/24	12(20.7%)	1(1.7%)	
6/36	10(17.2%)	16(27.6%)	
6/60	15(25.9%)	16(27.6%)	
K1(D)	43.89(1.36)	43.40(1.60)	0.07
K2(D)	44	44	0.21
Axial length(mm)	22.8(1.4)	23(1.6)	0.37
IOP(mmHg)	15.8(3.4)	14.6(2.9)	0.07

The mean age of the study participants was 60.2±7.9 years in foldable group versus 57.4±8.8 years in non-foldable group with a p-value of 0.21 indicating no statistically significant difference.

The gender distribution among patients undergoing cataract surgery was that in Group A, 50.0% were female and 50.0% were male, while in Group B, 51.7% were female and 48.3% were male.

The pre op BCVA, K1,K2, Axial length and IOP parameters were statistically insignificant.

Table 2: Postoperative Parameters in the Study Groups on Day 1

Post Op Day 1		Group A (F)		Group B (NF)		p-value
		n	n %	n	n %	
UCVA	6/6	13	22.4%	3	5.2%	0.01*
	6/9	33	56.9%	32	55.2%	
	6/12	12	20.7%	17	29.3%	
	6/18	0	0.0%	6	10.3%	
logMAR UCVA	0.00	13	22.4%	3	5.2%	0.01*
	0.20	33	56.9%	32	55.2%	
	0.30	12	20.7%	17	29.3%	
	0.50	0	0.0%	6	10.3%	
BCVA	6/6	21	36.2%	6	10.3%	0.01*
	6/9	37	63.8%	45	77.6%	
	6/12	0	0.0%	7	12.1%	
logMAR BCVA	0.00	2	34.5%	6	10.3%	0.01*
	0.20	37	63.8%	45	77.6%	
	0.30	0	0.0%	7	12.1%	
		MEAN	SD	MEAN	SD	
K1(D)		43.3	1.3	43.0	1.5	0.13
K2(D)		44.2	1.3	44.3	1.6	0.69
Axis		121.9	6.4	124.1	9.7	0.14
Mean astigmatism		0.83	0.65	1.3	0.42	0.01

*p value is statistically significant.

On postoperative day 1, Group A showed significantly better UCVA and BCVA compared to Group B patients, as evidenced by higher percentage of patients achieving 6/6 UCVA (22.4% vs. 5.2%, p = 0.01) and 6/6 BCVA (36.2% vs. 10.3%, p = 0.01).

These findings suggest superior immediate visual outcomes with foldable IOLs.

There was no statistically significant difference in corneal parameters between Group A and Group B patients, as indicated by similar mean values for K1, K2, and Axis (p > 0.05 for all).

Group A patients exhibited significantly lower mean surgically induced astigmatism compared to Group B (p = 0.01).

Table 3: Postoperative Visual Acuity in the Study Groups at 1 month

1 st month		Group A (F)		Group B (NF)		p-value
		n	n%	n	n%	
UCVA	6/6	24	41.4%	7	12.1%	0.01*
	6/9	34	58.6%	43	74.1%	
	6/12	0	0.0%	7	12.1%	
	6/18	0	0.0%	1	1.7%	
logMAR UCVA	0.00	24	41.4%	7	12.1%	0.01*
	0.20	34	58.6%	43	74.1%	
	0.30	0	0.0%	7	12.1%	
	0.50	0	0.0%	1	1.7%	
BCVA	6/6	33	56.9%	15	25.9%	0.01*
	6/9	25	43.1%	43	74.1%	
	0.00	33	56.9%	15	25.9%	
	0.20	25	43.1%	43	74.1%	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
	K1 (D)	43.3	1.3	42.5	1.5	0.01*
	K2 (D)	44.1	1.3	44.0	1.5	0.69
	Axis (Degree)	121.3	6.5	128.1	7.9	0.01*
	Mean astigmatism	0.80	0.35	1.47	0.22	0.01*

*p value is statistically significant.

At one month postoperative, Group A patients demonstrated significantly better visual outcomes compared to Group B, with higher percentage of patients achieving 6/6 UCVA (41.4% vs. 12.1%, $p = 0.01$) and 6/6 BCVA (56.9% vs. 25.9%, $p = 0.01$). These findings highlight the superior visual acuity achieved with foldable IOLs at one month. Group A patients had significantly lower mean K1 and K2 values compared to Group B, with p-values of 0.01 and 0.69, respectively, while axis showed a statistically significant difference as well ($p = 0.01$). Group A patients exhibited significantly lower mean surgically induced astigmatism compared to Group B ($p = 0.01$)

Table 4: Postoperative Parameters in the Study Groups at the end of third month

3 rd month		Group A		Group B		p-value
		N	n %	n	n%	
UCVA	6/6	39	67.2%	28	48.3%	0.03 *
	6/9	19	32.8%	30	51.7%	
logMAR UCVA	0.00	39	67.2%	28	48.3%	0.03*
	0.20	19	33.8%	30	51.7%	
BCVA	6/6	48	82.8%	37	65.5%	0.03*
	6/9	10	17.2%	21	34.5%	
logMAR BCVA	0.00	48	82.8%	37	65.5%	0.03*
	0.20	10	17.2%	21	34.5%	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
	K1(D)	42.1	1.5	43.3	1.3	0.01*
	K2(D)	43.2	1.4	44.6	1.3	0.01*
	Axis(degree)	122.6	6.6	128.1	7.9	0.01*
	Mean Astigmatism	1.16	0.27	1.30	0.35	0.01*

*p value is statistically significant.

At the end of third month postoperative, Group A showed significantly better visual outcomes compared to Group B, with higher percentage of patients achieving 6/6 UCVA (67.2% vs. 48.3%, $p = 0.03$) and 6/6 BCVA (82.8% vs. 65.5%, $p = 0.03$). This suggests sustained superior visual acuity with foldable IOLs at the end of three months. Group A patients exhibited significantly lower mean values for K1, K2, and axis compared to Group B ($p < 0.01$ for all), indicating a more favorable corneal profile in the foldable IOL group. Group A patients had significantly lower mean surgically induced astigmatism compared to Group B ($p = 0.01$).

DISCUSSION

In our study, we conducted a comparative analysis of phacoemulsification procedures with both foldable and non-foldable IOLs to benefit economically non-affording patients.

In our study, the UCVA on Post Op Day 1 the p-value of 0.01 indicates a statistically significant difference in UCVA outcomes between foldable and non-foldable IOLs in our study.

Similarly, in a study by Shashi et al., visual outcomes on Day 1 in foldable IOL patients shows that 76.0% of patients achieved good vision, 22.0% achieved borderline vision, and 2.0% had poor vision. For non-foldable IOLs, 72.0% of patients achieved good vision, 20.0% achieved borderline vision, and 8.0% had poor vision. The p-value is 0.1493, indicating no statistically significant difference in visual outcomes between foldable and non-foldable IOLs in their study.⁽⁸⁾

Conversely, Tyagi et al. in a study reported that on post op Day 1 UCVA in foldable IOL shows that 76.0%,24.0%,0.0% of patients had vision in the range of 6/6-6/18, 6/24-6/60, and less than 6/60 respectively. In non-foldable IOL group, 69.2%, 30.8%,0.0% of patients had vision in the range of 6/6-6/18, of 6/24-6/60, less than 6/60 respectively. The p-value of 0.294 indicate no statistically significant difference in UCVA outcomes between foldable and non-foldable IOLs in their study.⁽⁹⁾

In our study, on post operative Day 1, mean SIA for foldable IOLs group was 0.83 ± 0.65 , while for non-foldable IOLs it was significantly higher at 1.3 ± 0.42 . The p-value of 0.01 indicates that the difference in SIA between foldable and non-foldable IOLs is statistically significant.

In a study by Awargaonkar et al, on Day 1 mean SIA in foldable IOL patients was much lower at 0.04 ± 0.2 , compared to 0.14 ± 0.41 in rigid IOL patients. However, the difference noted was not statistically significant with p-value of 0.121.⁽⁷⁾

The study shows that at postoperative 1 month, the p-value of 0.01 indicates a statistically significant difference in UCVA outcomes between foldable and non-foldable IOLs in our study. Conversely, in a study by Garg et al., postoperative 1-month UCVA results in foldable IOL group showed that 100% of patients had vision in the range of 6/6-6/18 and in non-foldable IOL group, 99% of patients had vision in the range of 6/6-6/18, 1% had

vision in the range of 6/24-6/60. The p-value of 0.333 indicates no statistically significant difference in UCVA outcomes. ⁽¹⁰⁾

In this study, postoperative 1-month BCVA results for foldable IOL group showed that 56.9%, 43.1% achieved 6/6 and 6/9 vision respectively. In non-foldable IOL group 25.9%,74.1% achieved 6/6 and 6/9 vision respectively. The p-value of 0.01 indicates a statistically significant difference in BCVA outcomes between two groups.

In our study, at post operative 1 month follow-up, mean SIA in the foldable IOL group was observed to be 0.80 ± 0.35 , while it was 1.47 ± 0.22 in non-foldable IOL group. The difference between the groups was statistically significant with a p-value of 0.01. which was similar to study by Garg et al. reported an SIA of 0.55 ± 0.43 in foldable IOLs and 1.06 ± 0.46 in non-foldable IOLs, with a p-value of <0.001 . While the mean SIA values in the current study are higher for both foldable and non-foldable IOLs, studies consistently demonstrate that foldable IOLs result in less SIA compared to non-foldable IOLs. ⁽¹⁰⁾

In our study, in post-op 3rd month, in foldable IOL group BCVA values were 82.8% of patients achieved a BCVA of 6/6, while 17.2% had a BCVA of 6/9. In non-foldable IOL group, 65.5% of patients achieved a BCVA of 6/6, and 34.5% had a BCVA of 6/9. The difference between the groups was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.03. In comparison, Garg et al. in a study reported the following BCVA results at post- op 3rd month in foldable IOLs group, 97%and 3% had a BCVA of 6/6 and 6/9 respectively while in non-foldable IOL group 95% and 5% of patients had a BCVA of 6/6 and 6/9 respectively. The difference between the groups was not statistically significant with a p-value of 0.38. ⁽¹⁰⁾

In our study, in post-op 3rd month, SIA in foldable IOL patients was observed to be 1.16 ± 0.27 , while in non-foldable IOL patients it was 1.30 ± 0.35 . The difference between the groups was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.01. Garg et al in a study reported significantly lower SIA values in foldable IOLs group with a mean SIA of $0.51. \pm 0.44$ while it was 1.05 ± 0.48 in the non-foldable IOLs group, with a p-value of $<0. 001$.This indicates that the difference in SIA between the two groups was statistically significant which is in agreement with our study. ⁽¹⁰⁾

Mean and standard deviation of preoperative and post-operative astigmatism on 1st day, 1month and 3rd month in Foldable IOL group was 0.56 ± 0.22 D, 0.83 ± 0.65 D, 0.80 ± 0.35 D and 1.16 ± 0.27 D whereas in Non foldable IOL group was 0.70 ± 0.38 D, 1.33 ± 0.42 D, 1.47 ± 0.22 D and 1.30 ± 0.35 D respectively.

CONCLUSION

Phacoemulsification with the insertion of a foldable IOL via a 2.8mm clear corneal incision, results in reduced postoperative astigmatism when compared to phacoemulsification with a non-foldable IOL implanted through a 6mm sclerocorneal tunnel. While patients' primary concern lies in the ultimate visual outcome, which is slightly better in the foldable IOL group, it is noteworthy that both options yield excellent visual results when performed by skilled cataract surgeons. Hence, although opting for

phacoemulsification with a foldable IOL over rigid PMMA IOL can ensure better visual outcomes, in certain conditions such as poor affordability, poor cornea, dense hard cataracts SICS can be done to provide good visual outcome also. Further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow up periods are warranted to evaluate long-term outcomes.

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